

Solvents A, C, E can be used for the separation of phenyl thiourea from diphenyl thioureas while A, B, C, E can be used for the separation of phenyl thiourea from dibenzyl thiourea. Solvents E and F can give separation of *o*-tolyl and *m*-tolyl thiourea while A, D, E and F can be used for the separation of *o*-tolyl from *p*-tolyl thiourea. *o*-Methoxy and *p*-methoxy phenyl thiourea can be best separated in solvent C alone.

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Isomorphous Replacement of Hydroxyl Group by Fluoride Group in Kaolinite and Bentonite

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THE clay minerals kaolinite and bentonite were studied for isomorphous replacement of hydroxyl ion by fluoride ion¹⁻¹⁴. Kaolinite has as many as 6 OH groups on the surface of the crystal lattice and in the case of bentonite (montmorillonite) comparatively less hydroxyls are present on the crystal surface. Experimental data obtained, are present on the crystal surface. Experimental data obtained, are presented in Tables 1 and 2, and shown graphically in diagrams 1 to 6.

Diagram 1 indicates changes in *pH* on adding increasing proportions of 0.1 *M* solutions of different fluoride salts to normal kaolinite and bentonite and H-kaolinite and H-bentonite.

Diagrams 2 to 6 indicate liberated hydroxyl ion proportion with time factor.

TABLE 1. ACTION OF HYDROFLUORIC ACID ON DIFFERENT CLAYS

Sample No.	SiO ₂ /R ₂ O ₃	Boiling for ½ hr. wt. loss v/v		
		1% HF	5.0% HF	10% HF
2	1.62	47.6	—	77.7
12	1.21	52.0	72.0	85.5
14	2.38	54.0	64.3	65.4
16	1.59	38.8	60.9	61.3
18	2.19	35.4	42.8	54.3
30	1.17	47.1	94.2	94.2
33	2.92	41.4	86.7	90.6
35	1.10	51.0	95.5	98.0
36	1.10	49.8	92.8	94.4
Kaolinite	1.08	52.7	98.7	98.8
Bentonite	—	46.5	88.7	91.0

Discussion

The effect of different concentrations of hydrofluoric acid on clay was studied. The data (Table 1) show that 10% HF will cause as much as 98% kaolinite and 91% bentonite to enter into solution. This indicates complete breakdown of the crystal lattice of the clay minerals. The higher degree of disruption of the crystal lattice in the case of kaolinite with hydrofluoric acid may be explained on the ground that it may be due to preferential extraction of Aluminium from the lattice, leaving an intermediate silica phase which dissolves to form fluo-silicic acid.

The possible reaction may be :

Theoretically with an increase in the concentration of hydrofluoric acid, only 86% dissolution is possible, but in practice dissolution in the case of kaolinite reaches 98%. To explain this high value, it is believed that the following reaction may also be simultaneously taking place :

TABLE 2. EFFECT OF KF (NEUTRAL SOLUTION) ON OH- LIBERATION

	0.1M		0.5M	
	Boiling for 2 hr.	Without boiling 6 days	Boiling for 2 hr.	Without boiling 6 days
	g/100 g.			
Bentonite	1.050	1.038	2.100	1.220
Kaolinite	0.680	0.510	3.120	1.660

The comparative behaviour of interaction of fluorides with kaolinite and bentonite is shown by changes in *pH* when normal kaolinite, H-kaolinite, normal bentonite and H-bentonite are reacted with 0.1 *M* HF, 0.1 *M* NaF and 0.1 *M* NH₄F (Diagram 1).

Reaction of HF with H-bentonite and H-kaolinite indicated identical behaviour and it was found that the pH dropped from 4.0 to about 2.5. However, in the case of reaction normal bentonite and 0.1 M HF the pH decreased from 9.5 to 3.5. It was an indication that normal bentonite may be initially highly hydrolysed while H-kaolinite or H-bentonite are not hydrolysed to that extent. Of course, this does not signify whether fluoride-hydroxyl replacement takes place, but it can be indirectly concluded because addition of HF does not bring about an appreciable decrease which would occur if the solution was more concentrated with HF alone.

In the case of reaction of 0.1 M NaF with H-kaolinite and H-bentonite it was found that with H-bentonite and pH increases from 4.0 to 5.4 while for H-kaolinite it changes from 4.0 to 7.2. This indicates a higher amount of hydroxyl has been replaced in the case of kaolinite than bentonite. It is very likely that reaction with kaolinite was faster due to the hydroxyl groups being on the surface.

Continuous replacement of hydroxyl by fluoride in bentonite was indicated, but in the case of kaolinite the liberated alkali also reacted with surface fluorides and the reaction has a different pattern than that of bentonite (Dia. 2,3,4). Potassium fluoride appeared to be more reactive than NaF. Results in Table 2 indicate clearly that in 0.5 M solution the breakdown mechanism can be preferred. Results in dissolution experiments (Table 1) indicate that entrance of as much as 98% of kaolinite and 91% of bentonite into solution, provides an additional evidence to breakdown mechanism.

The nature of the curves in diagram 2 to 6 indicate that the reaction product might be taking part and therefore the released hydroxyl groups get a chance to interact with adsorbed fluorides, this appears to be in concurrence with Huang and Jackson's observation that if the reaction products are removed then HCl titrable OH is rapidly released. However, results in diagram 2 to 4 can be compared with Fig. 1 of Huang and Jackson, and therefore it may be argued on a similar basis that release of hydroxyl may be due to formation of the complex K_3AlF_6 , as these workers have already examined absence of fluoride in the mineral after interaction with a fluoride solution. Even then it may be possible that in dilute solutions replacement of hydroxyl by fluoride can be seen by comparing diagram 4 for kaolinite clay (0.1 M KF) while in higher concentrations of the solution 0.5 M KF, there may be both, the replacement as well as the mineral disruption. The breakdown is more vigorous in KF than in NaF solution so far as kaolinite is concerned (Compare Diag. 3 and 5).

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Alkali was continuously released by small addition of fluoride solution but after a certain stage in kaolinite there was stagnation and no more alkali is released, while in bentonite the reaction was certainly slower but more continuous (Dia. 6). In the case of kaolinite it was found that a considerable amount of alkali was liberated in the initial stages, i.e., within 60 min as much as 0.795 g. alkali was liberated and within 125 min almost all the possible alkali, 1.025 gms. was liberated and then no more alkali was liberated. The liberation of a good amount of titrable alkali in the initial stages of reaction can be accounted for by the presence of exposed surface hydroxyl groups of the kaolinite crystal lattice.

The constancy in the liberated titrable alkali in the case of kaolinite, with the time for the reaction, is indicating the absence of any further reaction.

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Book Review

PHYSICAL ADSORPTION ON IONIC SOLIDS

BY

R. H. VAN DONGEN (Uitgeverij Waltman—Delft (1972))

The author has dealt the fundamental aspects of physical adsorption in chapters II & III, whereas chapters IV through VII are chiefly attuned to the analysis of experimental adsorption data. In chap. VIII, theoretical findings are compared to the experimental adsorption data. Interaction of adsorbed molecules with the electric field of the ionic adsorbents has been specially considered and also the transition from mobile to supermobile adsorption in brief. Special attention has been paid to the two

dimensional critical temperature of A., Kr., Xe, N on these ionic solid, In short it may be said that the author has tried to present the subject matter of such interesting topics very nicely and lucidly and the book will be useful to these who are interested in the field. The binding and printing are good.

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